

Table S10a: Soil profile description according to FAO (2006) and WRB (2015) and further details regarding the sampling and location of the soil profiles.

soil profile	horizon	sampling time	depth [cm]	coordinates of sample pits (WGS84)
Cambisol	O	May 2019	+3 cm	48°34'43.8"N 9°03'48.5"E
	Ah	November 2016, May 2019	0-9 cm	
	Bw1	May 2019	16-40 cm	
Podzol	O	May 2019	+7 cm	48°34'40.4"N 9°03'51.1"E
	Ah	May 2019	0-6 cm	
Stagnosol	O	May 2019	+4 cm	48°34'44.7"N 9°03'48.0"E
	Ah	May 2019	0-10 cm	

Soil Physico-chemical parameters characterization (detection limits)

Table S10b: Detection limits and quality control (Certified Standard IVA 33802150, sediment (high organic), lot: 155656, 144137) for CN measurements. idl= instrumental detection limit (for a sample weight of 0.04 g), wt%= weight percentage, RSD= relative standard deviation.

element	N [wt%]	C [wt%]
idl [wt%]	0.03	0.1
IVA 33802150 (n= 196)		
Average:	0.65	8.03
RSD [%]:	4.57	3.28
%difference to target value:	98.6	102
in-house leave standard (n= 10)		
Average:	2.27	48.5
RSD [%]:	5.40	4.31

Table S10c: Overview of analytical details for major and trace elements analyzed by ICP-OES after acid pressure digestion. Methodological detection limits (mdl) calculated based on extraction blind solutions (3-times standard deviation, n= 68) and a sample targeted weight of 0.05g. Element concentrations in litter samples were corrected to the certified standard materials BCR-129 (hay powder) and BCR-141 (plankton). RSD= relative standard deviation. amf= additional material information; cv= certified value, iv= information value, indv= indicative value, na= no value available.

element:	Na	K	Mg	Ca	Al	Fe	Mn	P	Ba	Sr	V
wavelength [nm] measuring mode	589.592 radial	766.490 axial	285.213 radial	317.933 radial	396.153 axial	238.204 axial	257.610 radial	213.617 axial	233.527 axial	407.771 radial	311.071 axial
mdl [mg kg ⁻¹]:	58.2	8.56	63.3	330	66.3	3.53	1.17	2.21	0.64	0.59	0.04
standard:	BCR-129	BCR-129	BCR-129	BCR-129	BCR-141	BCR-129	BCR-141	BCR-129	BCR-141	BCR-141	BCR-141
n	20	20	19	20	18	20	19	20	19	19	19
average concentration [mg kg ⁻¹]:	2756	27584	1145	4954	1843	87	226	1965	24.4	201	7.20
RSD [%]:	7	11	8	9	8	10	5	6	6	5	6
target value [mg kg ⁻¹]:	3491	33800	1450	6400	1800	114	299	2360	31.0	261	8.10
target value type:	amf	cv	cv	cv	iv	amf	cv	cv	iv	indv	cv
average recovery rate [%]:	79	82	79	77	102	76	76	83	79	77	89
applied correction factor:	1.27	1.23	1.27	1.29	0.98	1.31	1.32	1.20	1.27	1.30	1.12

